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Effects of Marketing Capability on Competitiveness of Listed Investment Firms in Kenya

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Abstract

In today's dynamic and competitive business environment shaped by globalization and rapid technological change, organizations rely on unique capabilities to remain competitive. Guided by Porter's Theory of Competitiveness and the Resource-Based View, this study examined the effect of marketing capability on the competitiveness of listed investment firms in Kenya. Using descriptive and correlational research designs, data were collected from 273 respondents—top, middle, and functional managers—from five listed firms through structured questionnaires. Validity and reliability were ensured through expert review, pilot testing, and Cronbach's alpha. Data analysis employed descriptive (means, standard deviations) and inferential statistics (correlation and regression), with results presented in tables and figures. The findings revealed that marketing capability plays a crucial role in firm competitiveness. Firms that effectively leverage market knowledge, implement strong customer acquisition strategies, and manage customer relationships achieve superior performance. The study concluded that marketing capability significantly influences competitiveness and recommended that firms integrate adaptability, information management, innovation, and marketing capabilities. These interconnected capabilities should be developed holistically to reinforce one another and sustain competitive advantage.

Key words: *Marketing Capability, Competitiveness, Listed Investment Firms, Kenya*

1. Introduction

In today's increasingly competitive and complex business environment, organizations must rely on effective management capabilities to gain and sustain competitive advantages. Organizational capabilities refer to the specialized knowledge, competencies, resources, and strategies that firms develop to respond efficiently to competitive pressures and market dynamics (Thompson, Peteraf, Gamble, & Strickland, 2015). These capabilities determine a firm's ability to innovate, adapt quickly to changes, exploit market opportunities, and sustain market leadership.

Competitiveness is particularly crucial in the investment management industry due to the sector's dynamic nature, heavy reliance on investor confidence, and vulnerability to economic fluctuations. The performance and growth of investment management firms are directly linked to their ability to deliver superior value to their clients, differentiate their offerings, and respond effectively to economic and technological changes (Kogei, 2024). Increased competition, driven by globalization, regulatory shifts, technological advancement, and evolving consumer preferences, has heightened the need for strategic organizational capabilities, especially in adaptability, innovation, information, and marketing.

Globally, competitiveness in the investment management sector has been heavily influenced by disruptive technologies, investor shifts toward passive and ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) portfolios, and stricter compliance requirements. For instance, in the United States, firms like Vanguard and BlackRock have had to continuously evolve their organizational capabilities to maintain cost leadership and technology-driven service delivery amid fee compression and regulatory scrutiny (PwC, 2023). In Europe, firms have grappled with post-Brexit adjustments and sustainability disclosure regulations, which require strategic innovation and robust information systems to stay competitive (EY Global Wealth Management Report, 2022).

Marketing capability is the firm's ability to effectively combine market knowledge, organizational resources, and marketing skills to identify and respond to customer needs, thereby enhancing value creation and competitive positioning (Fernandez, Del Rio Varela & Bande, 2010). Organizations with robust marketing capabilities utilize customer insights, effective channel management, strategic pricing, targeted communication, and strong brand management to gain competitive advantage.

In competitive industries, marketing capability helps firms anticipate market shifts, influence customer choices, and effectively respond to competitive pressures (Abidemi, Halim & Alshuaibi, 2017). This capability is critical as it allows firms to differentiate their offerings, foster customer loyalty, and expand market share. For instance, microfinance institutions in Kenya significantly improved their market performance and competitive edge by leveraging strategic marketing capabilities such as product innovation,

effective promotional strategies, and customer relationship management (Odhiambo, Kibera & Musyoka, 2015). Thus, marketing capability directly impacts a firm's competitiveness by enhancing its responsiveness to market dynamics and customer demands.

2. Study Objective

The main objective of the study was to determine the effects of marketing capability on competitiveness of listed investment firms in Kenya.

3. Literature Review

3.1 Theoretical Review – Resource-based View Theory

The theory posits that firms with strategic resources, full control over them, and unique capabilities to exploit them can attain and sustain competitive advantage. Resources are classified into physical, human, and organizational capital (Mainardes, Ferreira & Tontini, 2011). The theory assumes that firms possess unique bundles of tangible and intangible assets and can generate competencies from them, thereby achieving competitiveness (Kraipetch, Kanjanawasee & Prachyapruit, 2013). However, RBT has been criticized for overlooking variations in resource levels among firms, government control, market entry and exit barriers, and regulatory constraints that affect organizational performance (Nielsen, D'haen, & Reenberg, 2012). In this study, RBT is relevant as it explains how adaptability, information, marketing, and innovation capabilities enhance the competitiveness of listed investment firms in Kenya. Possession of resources such as human capital, strategic locations, technical expertise, and marketing strengths provides these firms with an edge. Ultimately, competitiveness depends on how efficiently and effectively firms utilize these resources, with continuous innovation and unique exploitation strategies sustaining their market position.

3.2 Empirical Review

Recent empirical studies in the U.S. context have emphasized the strategic role of marketing capability in enhancing firm competitiveness, particularly among listed investment firms. Hu et al. (2023) examined the intersection of marketing capability and ESG performance, revealing that firms with superior marketing capabilities not only achieved higher ESG scores but also demonstrated improved investment efficiency. This synergy was especially pronounced under conditions of low economic policy uncertainty and minimal agency costs, suggesting that marketing capability acts as a strategic lever in optimizing firm competitiveness in dynamic environments.

Similarly, Cataltepe et al. (2022) argued that marketing capability is a critical determinant of superior firm performance in competitive consumer markets. Their findings confirmed that marketing capability—encompassing pricing, product development, and communication—significantly contributes to sustained competitive advantage and market positioning among U.S.-listed firms.

In Europe, marketing capability has been empirically linked to international performance and strategic competitiveness. A study by Cinjarevic et al. (2023) found that marketing capabilities positively influenced the internationalization success of investment firms, enabling them to adopt high-order entry modes and outperform competitors in foreign markets. This was particularly evident in firms that integrated market knowledge into dynamic marketing strategies.

Additionally, Köylüoğlu et al. (2021) conducted a literature review across European firms and concluded that marketing investments consistently yielded positive returns in terms of profitability, firm value, and sales growth. Their synthesis highlighted that marketing capability is not merely a functional asset but a strategic investment that drives competitiveness in increasingly globalized financial markets.

Further, Susanto et al. (2023) emphasized that marketing capability serves as a foundational element for competitive advantage in Asian markets. Their empirical analysis confirmed that firms with robust marketing systems—especially in pricing and customer engagement—were better positioned to navigate market volatility and sustain growth.

Duah et al. (2024) explored the mediating role of resource orchestration capability in the relationship between marketing capability and firm performance. Using data from 379 firms across the continent, the study found that marketing capability significantly enhanced competitiveness when coupled with strategic resource deployment. This highlights the importance of managerial alignment and operational integration in leveraging marketing assets.

Moreover, Cheruon et al. (2023) demonstrated that marketing capability is a non-transferable resource that improves the productivity of other organizational assets, thereby fostering sustained competitive advantage. Their findings reinforce the strategic value of marketing capability in African investment firms operating in complex and resource-constrained environments.

Frankwick (2023) investigated the relationship between marketing capability, strategy implementation, and firm performance among small listed firms. The study revealed that effective implementation of marketing strategies significantly moderated the

impact of marketing capability on both market and financial performance. This suggests that execution is as critical as capability in driving competitiveness.

Additionally, Nyangao (2018) examined competitive strategies among investment firms listed on the Nairobi Securities Exchange. His findings indicated that differentiation and focus strategies, rooted in marketing capability, were instrumental in enhancing firm competitiveness. The study emphasized the need for firms to invest in market intelligence and customer-centric approaches to remain competitive in Kenya's evolving financial landscape.

Kyengo, Muathe, and Kinyua (2019), analyzed the how marketing capability affect firm performance of food processing firms in Nairobi city county, Kenya. This adopted explanatory and descriptive research designs were adopted and positivism research philosophy. Semi-structured questionnaires were applied by the study to obtain primary data. Collected data was analyzed through descriptive and inferential statistics while quantitative data was analyzed through content analysis. The study found out that marketing capability affected performance positively. The study recommended for management of food processing firms to ensure that enough resources are availed for advertising activities.

4. Research Design

This study employed descriptive and correlational research designs to examine the relationship between organizational capabilities—adaptability, information, innovation, and marketing—and competitiveness of listed investment firms in Kenya.

The target population consisted of 656 employees from five firms listed on the Nairobi Securities Exchange, selected for their regulatory visibility and industry relevance. Using Yamane's (1967) formula, a sample size of 248 respondents was determined and selected through stratified proportionate random sampling to ensure representation across managerial levels. Data were collected from both primary and secondary sources.

Primary data came from structured questionnaires, while secondary data were obtained from firm reports, financial statements, and industry publications. Content validity was established through expert review using the Content Validity Index (CVI), and reliability was confirmed with Cronbach's alpha (threshold ≥ 0.70). Ethical approval was secured through Kisii University and NACOSTI, followed by formal permissions from the participating firms.

Data analysis was conducted using SPSS version 28, applying both descriptive and inferential statistics, with results presented in tables, figures, and summary statistics for clarity and interpretation.

5. Research Analysis and Findings

5.1 Descriptive Statistics

The study aimed to examine the effects of marketing capability on competitiveness of listed investment firms in Kenya. Respondents were asked to indicate the extent to which they agreed with statements related to the marketing capabilities of their firms. Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics for these responses.

Table 1: Market Capability practices

Statement	Mean	Std. Dev.
The marketing function is central and plays a key role in strategic decisions.	3.015	1.423
The firm effectively utilizes market knowledge to drive competitive advantage.	4.240	0.876
Staff possesses strong marketing skills relevant to customer and market needs.	2.913	1.406
The firm allocates and uses marketing resources efficiently.	3.327	1.166
The firm has developed successful customer retention strategies.	3.286	1.522
Effective customer acquisition strategies have increased the firm's client base.	3.888	1.350

The respondents agreed that the firm effectively utilizes market knowledge to drive competitive advantage as shown by a mean of 4.240. This aligns with Kamboj, Goyal, and Rahman (2015), who argued that market knowledge is a critical resource that firms use to identify opportunities, make informed decisions, and enhance their competitive positioning. Respondents also agreed that effective customer acquisition strategies have increased the firm's client base as shown by a mean of 3.888. Abidemi, Halim, and Alshuaibi (2018) highlighted that well-designed customer acquisition strategies help businesses increase their market share by attracting a larger and more diverse customer base, which is consistent with the findings that customer acquisition is a key factor in enhancing competitiveness.

However, respondents were neutral on whether the firm allocates and uses marketing resources efficiently as shown by a mean of 3.327. This finding is consistent with Akdeni, Padron, and Calantone (2010), who argue that firms often struggle to allocate marketing resources optimally, which can limit their ability to fully exploit their marketing potential. Similarly, the respondents

were neutral on whether the firm has developed successful customer retention strategies as shown by a mean of 3.286. The importance of customer retention as a driver of long-term success is well documented in the literature, with Plessis (2013) noting that firms that excel in retaining customers typically achieve more sustainable growth and profitability.

The respondents were also neutral about whether the marketing function is central and plays a key role in strategic decisions as shown by a mean of 3.015. This is supported by the findings of Falciola, Jansen, and Rollo (2020), who noted that while marketing functions are important, their role in shaping strategic decisions can vary across firms. The respondents were also neutral about whether the staff possesses strong marketing skills relevant to customer and market needs as shown by a mean of 2.913. This finding reflects the literature by Karanja, Muathe, and Thuo (2014), which emphasized that having well-trained staff with strong marketing capabilities is crucial for firms to adapt to market demands and stay competitive.

5.2 Inferential Analysis

The study sought to evaluate the effect of market capability on competitiveness of listed investment firms in Kenya. Regression was used to establish the relational effect between the two variables as computed below.

Table 2: ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1136.492	1	1136.492	217.088	0.000
	Residual	1015.621	194	5.235		
	Total	2152.113	195			

The regression analysis presented in the ANOVA table indicates a statistically significant model. The total variation in the dependent variable is 2,152.113, which is partitioned into two components: the variation explained by the regression model (1,136.492) and the unexplained residual variation (1,015.621). The model has one predictor variable (df = 1), and the residual degrees of freedom are 194, suggesting a sample size of 195 observations.

The mean square for the regression is 1,136.492, while the mean square for the residuals is 5.235. The resulting F-statistic is 217.088, which is substantially large and indicates that the regression model explains a significant proportion of the variance in the outcome variable. The associated significance value (Sig. = 0.000) confirms that the model is statistically significant at conventional levels (p < 0.001). This implies that the predictor variable included in the model has a strong and meaningful relationship with the dependent variable, and the likelihood that this result occurred by chance is extremely low.

Table 3: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.727	0.528	0.526	2.288

The model summary provides key metrics that assess the strength and explanatory power of the regression model. The correlation coefficient (R) is 0.727, indicating a strong positive linear relationship between the independent and dependent variables. This suggests that as the predictor variable increases, the outcome variable tends to increase as well. The coefficient of determination (R Square) is 0.528, meaning that approximately 52.8% of the variance in the dependent variable is explained by the model. This is a substantial proportion, reflecting a reasonably strong model fit. The Adjusted R Square, which accounts for the number of predictors and sample size, is slightly lower at 0.526. This minimal reduction suggests that the model is not over fitted and that the predictor variable contributes meaningfully to explaining the outcome. Overall, the model demonstrates a strong and statistically reliable relationship, with over half of the variation in the dependent variable being accounted for by the predictor. If needed, I can help integrate this interpretation into a structured recommendation or institutional report.

Table 3: Regression Coefficients

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	6.077	1.024		5.539	0.000
Market capability	0.412	0.027	0.727	15.259	0.000

Predictors: (constant), Market capability

Dependent Variable: Firm Competitiveness

Table 3 revealed that the regression coefficients provided insights into the relationship between Market Capability and Firm Competitiveness. The model included a constant (intercept) and one predictor variable—Market Capability. The unstandardized coefficient (B) for the constant was 6.077, indicating that when Market Capability was zero, the expected value of Firm

Competitiveness was 6.077 units. This constant was statistically significant, with a t-value of 5.539 and a p-value (Sig.) of 0.000, confirming that the intercept differed significantly from zero.

The coefficient for Market Capability was 0.412, with a standard error of 0.027. This implied that for every one-unit increase in Market Capability, Firm Competitiveness increased by approximately 0.412 units, holding other factors constant. The standardized coefficient (Beta) was 0.727, which reflected a strong positive effect of Market Capability on Firm Competitiveness when measured in standard deviation units. This aligned with the earlier model summary and ANOVA results, reinforcing the strength of the relationship.

Hypothesis testing using the t-statistic further validated the significance of Market Capability. The t-value of 15.259 was exceptionally high, and the associated p-value was 0.000, indicating that the null hypothesis—that Market Capability had no effect on Firm Competitiveness—was confidently rejected. This confirmed that Market Capability was a statistically significant predictor of Firm Competitiveness at the 0.001 level.

The regression analysis demonstrated that Market Capability had a robust and statistically significant positive influence on Firm Competitiveness, both in practical and statistical terms. This finding supported strategic emphasis on enhancing market-related competencies to improve organizational performance. The study was in agreement with a study by Duah et al. (2024) showed that marketing capability enhances competitiveness when coupled with resource orchestration, highlighting the importance of managerial alignment in leveraging marketing assets.

Similarly, Cheruon et al. (2023) emphasized that marketing capability improves the productivity of other resources, thus sustaining competitive advantage in resource-constrained African markets. Frankwick (2023) further demonstrated that successful implementation of marketing strategies amplifies the impact of marketing capability on firm performance, underscoring the importance of execution in achieving competitiveness.

Nyangao (2018) established that marketing-driven differentiation and focus strategies were critical for the competitiveness of firms listed on the Nairobi Securities Exchange. Kyengo, Muathe, and Kinyua (2019) also found that marketing capability positively affected firm performance in Nairobi's food processing firms, recommending investment in advertising and customer satisfaction initiatives. These regional findings reinforce the present study's conclusion that marketing capability significantly contributes to competitiveness among listed investment firms in Kenya.

6. Conclusions and Recommendations

The study concluded that marketing capability significantly influences firm competitiveness. The research deduced that firms that effectively utilize market knowledge, develop robust customer acquisition strategies, and efficiently allocate marketing resources tend to achieve better performance. The study concluded that marketing capabilities play a vital role in differentiating firms, fostering customer loyalty, and driving market expansion. However, the research also concluded that there is room for improvement in terms of fully optimizing marketing resources and ensuring that customer retention strategies are consistently applied to maintain a competitive edge.

The research recommended that investment firms should work towards integrating their capabilities in adaptability, information management, innovation, and marketing. The study emphasized that these capabilities are interconnected and work together to create a competitive advantage. Therefore, firms should adopt a holistic approach to building and enhancing these capabilities to ensure that they complement each other and contribute to the overall competitiveness of the firm.

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